

TITLE OF THE PAPER MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE THEORY IN TEACHER'S TRAINING

Shri. Tandale Pramod Prakashrao
Assistant Professor
Tq. & Dist : Latur.

Dr.Kulkarni Nandkishor Hanmantrao
Principal
Renuka college of education, Renapur .
RBM M.Ed.college, Hatta
Tq. Vasmat Dist. Higoli.

Introduction :

Education needs the new trend and research work it enrich the quality of education. Psychology gives many important clarifications about educational process and it enhance the learning and teaching process always (Learning theories) and this theory focus on pedagogy. The theory of multiple intelligence based on the psychological base which focuses on student's learning style and academic achievement. The American psychologist Dr.Harvard Gardner define about multiple intelligence he mention that every person have many kind of intelligence which effect on his learning this different kind of intelligence have their own characteristic and if we identify that characteristic closely we get more information of that student. To know about this scenario we must implement this theory in our teacher's training also in theoretically and practically.

Multiple Intelligence Theory :-

In past psychologist say that intelligence is identify by body, faces, appearance. But Gardner appose that and prove the intelligence have many aspect .Gardner argues that the concept of intelligence as traditionally defined in psychometrics (IQ tests) does not describe the wide variety of cognitive abilities humans display.It means that the intelligence not be tested in one aspect.

Gardner say that the concept of intelligence as traditionally defined in psychometrics (IQ tests) does not sufficiently describe the wide variety of cognitive abilities humans display. For example, the theory tells that a child who learns to multiply easily is not necessarily more intelligent than a child who has stronger skills in another *kind* of intelligence.

According to that we must think to give global level knowledge to our student. PROGECT ZERO is tested and proved that MI is one of the new trend in Education. Our education must need this kind of new trends which bust our educational system. The student of teacher education must know the strength of his student and he also knows how to develop his student's carrier.

Multiple Intelligence and teacher training :-

As explain above the theory of Multiple intelligence is change our educational system and to getting this change we must interrelate this theory in our teacher education or our teacher training program either or in-service ,pre service.

In this all teacher training program we introduce multiple intelligence theory and train our teacher for use this kind of theory in their daily teaching we got outcome of economical investment in educational system. Teacher training program

go towards success if teacher know the strength of his each student and then he choose his teaching method and his teaching ads. Student also gets more knowledge with long term memory.

1) Pre service

Pre service training is on of largest learning stream which make a good teacher who are full of energy and fresh mentally and physically. One example in pre service training all stream of teacher training student must learn content com methodology.

Incorporation of Multiple Intelligence in CCM :-

To develop Indian education The NCTE introduces content cum methodology in 1978. The main principle of content cum methodology is to utilize a method according to the content. In content cum methodology, the following things should be considered. They are follows:

- 1) The content should be analyzed.
- 2) The teacher should proceed from analyses to synthesis.
- 3) The teacher should follow an adequate method of teaching to teach his subject.

Teacher must have to take responsibilities of his students learning. Hence teacher has to teach student to learn themselves. Knowledge commission also suggests that we must “Teach student how to learn.” Therefore now there is need content cum methodology should incorporate with MI Theory and make effective pre service training. Analyze content is most inportent thing in CCM for that teacher tell student the process of CCM in student’s on strength.

WHY WE INTRODUCE MI THEORY IN CCM ?

To get the effectiveness of this theory we must introduce student teacher this theory in his training period.

OBJECTIVES

- 1) To create awareness among student teachers about future teaching-learning process.
- 2) To enable the teacher educator to understand the integration of MI theory in CCM.

Hence to fulfill these objectives there is need of incorporating the MI THEORY while conducting the CCM workshop in teacher education institutions. Today there is need

that the educational institutions have to provide opportunities to the student teacher to learn them selves during the CCM workshop. Its procedure will be as follows:

- 1) Orientation about theoretical part of the CCM
- 2) Concept of the CCM
- 3) Subject Structure
- 4) Curriculum
- 5) Syllabus
- 6) Text Book
- 7) Analysis of Content
- 8) And planning of the lesson according to the CCM

However while doing the group work students must be given pair share work, co-operative learning, group discussion, and Poster sharing strategies. Hence they can enable to impart what they learn. So they can able to retain those aspects for a long time and they achieve their educational goal easily and effectively.

For the fulfillment of the second objective the teacher educators should be given proper training. So they can able to use skillfully the above mentioned strategies during the CCM workshop. Hence tomorrows teachers those are today's student teachers can able to practice the MI THEORY in the classroom.

CONCLUSION:-

The criticism on this MI theory is not applicable in Indian situation because our educational policy, infrastructure of teacher training institution and the syllabus in teachers training. The training colleges also impart this theory to be aware a future teacher for his tomorrow's carrier. Best part of MI theory it emphasize the individual importance of Sundance in teaching learning process.

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